

CORRELATION BETWEEN PROFILES OF THE TURMERIC GROWERS AND KNOWLEDGE LEVEL OF BIOFERTILIZERS

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Abstract

Present study was conducted in Wasmata block of Hingoli district of Maharashtra as it is a turmeric growing major area with the objectives to study the socio-economic characteristics of turmeric growers and its correlation with knowledge level of biofertilizers. 120 turmeric growers from 10 villages were randomly selected for study. An interview schedule seeking information of the turmeric growers with respect socio economic characteristics and knowledge about biofertilizer use was designed for the study. Data revealed that majority of turmeric growers were middle aged, educated up to higher secondary education, had medium land holding, income, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation. Characteristics education, occupation, annual income, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation of the turmeric growers had positive and highly significant Correlation with their knowledge level. Land holding had positive and significant Correlation with knowledge level. Age of the turmeric growers had negatively significant association with their knowledge. 53.00 per cent of total variation in knowledge of turmeric growers was explained by the all-selected independent variables.

Key Words: Correlation, Knowledge, Biofertilizers

Introduction

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) is one the most important and ancient spice of India, contains about 69.49 carbohydrate 6.30 protein, 5.10 oil and 3.50% mineral and other important elements in dry turmeric. (Swain *et al.*, 2007).

Turmeric contains up to 5 per cent essential oils and up to 5 per cent curcumin, a polyphenol. Turmeric has anti-inflammatory (painkiller), carminative, anti-flatulent, antimicrobial, anti-tumor, antioxidant, anti-arthritis, anti-amyloid, anti-ischemic and anti-inflammatory properties. (Singh *et al.*, 2017).

Turmeric is widely used as a spice in South Asia and Middle Eastern Cooking. Turmeric is an important ancient spice and ingredient of Indian dishes. Its use in India as culinary spice and in religious functions dates back in Vedic culture. It is grown in India from times immemorial. India is the world's largest producer, consumer and exporter of turmeric. India produces 80% of global turmeric production and exports 60 percent of world's export. Telangana is largest producer of turmeric followed by Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Orissa, West Bengal and Maharashtra (Anonymous 2020).

Crop production depends on use of quality inputs. Though the use of chemical fertilizer played a significant role in increasing crop production, its continuous use deteriorated soil fertility, destroyed soil microbial activity and disturbed environmental and ecological balance. Biofertilizers are believed to be the potential alternative to chemical fertilizers in improvement of soil fertility for sustainable crop production. Biofertilizer's production is also simple, requires less energy, capital and labour force as compared to chemical fertilizers. (Raimi *et al.* 2017).

As the area under turmeric cultivation in Wasmata taluka of Hingoli district the present study was undertaken with the specific objectives to study the socio-economic characteristics of the turmeric growers and to study the correlation between socio-economic characteristics of turmeric growers with knowledge level of biofertilizers.

Materials And Methods

Hingoli is one of the leading turmeric producer districts in Marathwada region of the Maharashtra State. Present for seeking information with respect socio economic characteristics and knowledge level of biofertilizers of the turmeric growers study was purposively conducted in Wasmata block. 120 farmers from 10 villages were randomly selected, who has cultivated turmeric crop on more than 0.20 ha area. An interview schedule including relevant questions to socio economic characters of turmeric growers

and their knowledge level of biofertilizer use was designed for the study. Data were collected by contacting the selected farmers at their homes or farm Knowledge of turmeric growers about use of biofertilizers was measured by using scoring technique. Score one was assigned for knowing the practice and score zero was assigned for lack of knowledge of practice. Based on total score of the turmeric growers, they were classified into three categories namely, 'low', 'medium' and 'high' by using mean and standard deviation. Statistical tools frequency, percentage, range, Karl Person's correlation coefficient was used for data analysis.

Results And Discussion

The data with regards to socio economic characters of turmeric growers is presented in table-1. Results of the table 1 revealed that majority (67.50 percent) of the turmeric growers were middle aged, whereas 19.17 per cent and 13.33 per cent turmeric growers belonged to old age group and young age group respectively.

With concern to education 27.50 per cent of the turmeric growers were educated up to higher secondary education followed by 23.33 per cent turmeric growers had 5th to 7th standard primary education, 14.16 per cent had secondary education, 10.83 per cent were illiterate and an equal percentage of turmeric growers had up to 4th standard primary education. 8.33 per cent turmeric growers were graduates, 02.52 per cent were post graduate and 2.50 per cent could able to read and write.

Nearly fifty percentage (49.16 %) of the turmeric growers had medium size of land holding followed by 20.00 per cent had marginal land holding. 19.17 percent turmeric growers were small land holder, 11.67 percent were semi medium land holder and none of the respondent had large land holding.

Majority (45.83%) of turmeric growers were engaged in farming occupation, whereas, 25.00 per cent of turmeric growers engaged in farming with labour, 12.50 per cent turmeric growers engaged in farming with subsidiary occupation, 11.67 per cent of turmeric growers were engaged in farming with business and 5.00 per cent turmeric growers were engaged in farming with service occupation.

It could be seen from Table-1, that 62.50 per cent of turmeric growers had medium income followed by 24.17 per cent and 13.33 per cent turmeric growers had high and low annual income respectively.

In case of social participation data revealed that, 58.33 per cent of the turmeric growers were having medium social participation

followed by 30.83 per cent and 10.84 per cent turmeric growers had low and high social participation, respectively.

It is observed from Table-1 that more than half (52.50%) turmeric growers were having medium level of extension contact. Whereas,

30.83 percent turmeric growers were having low extension contact and only 16.67 per cent had high level of extension contact.

More than half (66.67%) turmeric growers had medium level risk orientation whereas, 26.67 and 6.66 per cent of them had low- and high-level risk orientation respectively.

Table-1. Distribution of the turmeric growers according to their characteristics

N = 120

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Turmeric growers	
		Number	Per cent
Age			
1.	Young (up to 29 years)	16	13.33
2.	Middle age (30 to 50 years)	81	67.50
3.	Old (51 and above)	23	19.17
Mean = 39.45		SD = 10.25	
Education			
1.	Illiterate	13	10.83
2.	Literate (can only read and write)	03	2.50
3.	Primary education (up to 4th std)	13	10.83
4.	Primary education (5th - 7th std)	28	23.33
5.	Secondary education (8th - 10th std)	17	14.16
6.	Higher secondary education (11th & 12th)	33	27.50
7.	Graduate (above 12th)	10	8.33
8.	Post Graduate	03	2.52
Land holding			
1.	Marginal (Up to 1 ha.)	24	20.00
2.	Small (1.01 to 2.00 ha.)	23	19.17
3.	Semi medium (2.01 to 4.00 ha.)	14	11.67
4.	Medium (4.01 to 10.00 ha)	59	49.16
5.	Large (10.01 and above)	0	0.00
Occupation			
1.	Farming	55	45.83
2.	Farming + Labour	30	25.00
3.	Farming + Subsidiary Occupation	15	12.50
4.	Farming + Business	14	11.67
5.	Farming + Service	06	05.00
Annual Income			
1.	Low (Up to Rs.85729)	29	24.17
2.	Medium (Rs.85730 to255520)	75	62.50
3.	High (Rs. 25552 1 and above)	16	13.33
Mean = 1,70,625		SD = 84896	
Social Participation			
1.	Low (Up to 5)	37	30.83
2.	Medium (6 to 13)	70	58.33
3.	High (14 and above)	13	10.84
Mean = 8.91		SD = 4.07	
Extension Contact			
1.	Low (up to 13)	37	30.83
2.	Medium (14 to 21)	63	52.50
3.	High (22 and above)	20	16.67
Mean = 17.21		SD= 4.78	
Risk Orientation			
1.	Low (up to 12)	32	26.67
2.	Medium (13 to 23)	80	66.67
3.	High (24 and above)	08	6.66
Mean = 17.51		SD = 6.00	

Correlation between socio economic characters of turmeric growers and knowledge level of biofertilizers

Results of Table 2 revealed that characteristics education, occupation, annual income, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation of turmeric growers had positive and highly significant correlation with their knowledge level. Land holding had positive and significant correlation with knowledge level. Age of the turmeric growers had negatively significant association with their knowledge. This finding is supported by the findings of Shabbir (2012), Lad (2013).

Table-2. Correlation between socio economic characters of turmeric growers and their knowledge level
N=120

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Correlation coefficient (r)
1.	Age	-0.197*
2.	Education	0.395**
3.	Land holding	0.230*
4.	Occupation	0.300**
5.	Annual income	0.330**
6.	Social participation	0.554**
7.	Extension contact	0.378**
8.	Risk orientation	0.495**

* Significant at 0.05 level of probability.

** Significant at 0.01 level of probability.

Multiple linear regressions of independent variables with knowledge

The data pertaining to the correlation between dependent variable knowledge with independent variables of turmeric growers were analyzed and presented in Table-3.

It was observed from Table-3, that coefficient of determination (R^2) of the independent variables was 0.53. It indicated that 53.00 per cent

of total variation in knowledge of turmeric growers was explained by the all selected independent variables. It was observed that, amongst independent variables of farmers, five variables education, occupation, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation were positively and highly significant and age and annual income were. Land holding found negatively non-significant.

Table-3 Distribution of turmeric growers according to their Correlation between independent variables with the knowledge level
N= 120

Sr. No.	Independent variables	Regression coefficient (Bi)	Standard error	't' value
1.	Age	0.037	0.039	0.941 NS
2.	Education	0.599	0.220	2.718*
3.	Land holding	-0.008	0.106	-0.081 NS
4.	Occupation	0.932	0.255	3.645*
5.	Annual income	3.002	3.838	0.782 NS
6.	Social participation	0.309	0.086	3.575*
7.	Extension contact	0.231	0.067	3.411*
8.	Risk orientation	0.150	0.059	2.514*

$R^2 = 0.53$ F-value = 15.68

Note: * Significant at 0.01 % level of probability

NS= Non significant

Summery And Conclusions

The characteristics education, occupation, annual income, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation of turmeric growers had positive and highly significant correlation with their knowledge level. Land holding had positive and significant correlation with knowledge level. Age of the turmeric growers had negatively significant association with their knowledge.

It was observed that, amongst independent variables of farmers, five variables education, occupation, social participation, extension contact and risk orientation were positively and highly significant and age and annual income were. Land holding found negatively non-significant.

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